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**Submission to the AAS Accessing Australia's Research
Collections stakeholder consultation**

*The National Imaging Facility Museums and Collections Special
Interest group*

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The National Imaging Facility Museums and Collections Special Interest Group

The National Imaging Facility (NIF) Museums Special Interest group is a community of practitioners from the natural history collections sector who are engaged with three-dimensional (3D) imaging of biodiversity collections. It includes curators, collection managers, academic researchers, digitisation and informatics staff, and staff of several NIF nodes who support the community's imaging efforts. Our quarterly meetings provide a forum to discuss the challenges, latest developments, and best-practice in the area of 3D specimen imaging, both practical (e.g. use of NIF infrastructure; technical or storage capacity) and policy-related (e.g. copyright/IP issues and metadata standards).

The importance of 3D imaging in future-proofing biodiversity collections.

The need for access to the 3D structure of biodiversity objects is a core requirement of diverse disciplines in the academic, industrial, and government sectors. More traditionally, physical representations of the unique Australian biodiversity have been the mainstay of fundamental research in areas such as evolutionary biology, palaeontology, taxonomy and ecology. Modern use cases include pest and invasive species management, biosecurity, agriculture, education, research, conservation and public engagement and outreach. The impact of biodiversity collections to these fields stands to increase exponentially as the capacity for 3D imaging accelerates. This includes vastly improved access to collections by the public, both in museum exhibitions, online displays, and producing 3D prints for hands-on experiences of rare specimens. Another example of impact is the advent of reference collections of 3D objects to support the identification of species, which will substantially improve the use of collections in conservation, ecology, academic biodiversity research, as well as industrial applications such as biosecurity and agriculture/pest management. The application of these innovations is already well advanced in other parts of the world, such as the US. A good example is the NSF-funded oVert project (<https://www.floridamuseum.ufl.edu/overt/>), which is in the process of CT scanning and publishing 20,000 vertebrate specimens open-access on the MorphoSource platform. However, Australia is still in the early phases of adoption. Given our unique and extraordinary biodiversity, of which over 80% are endemic; it therefore critical that we catch up.

In the context of a National Approach to Biodiversity Collections, 3D biodiversity imaging such as surface/Computed Tomography [CT] scanning and photogrammetry represents one of the most important aspects of “extended specimens” because it has the potential to make collections accessible to all stakeholder communities at a vast scale. Physical biodiversity objects currently exist within a patchwork of state museums, commonwealth, agriculture, zoo and university collections, with widely varying accessibility and governance. This makes access inefficient and inequitable, of inconsistent standard, potentially damaging to specimens due to multiple handling, not replicable, and costly when travel to collections is required. It also prevents direct access and engagement of the general public to this mostly publicly funded research infrastructure.

Three-dimensional digital imagery can be more informative than the actual objects; it allows custodians of valuable material to publish their data as high-fidelity 3D models, while minimising object damage, or even retaining 3D representations of specimens that need to be sampled destructively e.g. for DNA. This replicability and shareability also makes 3D biodiversity imaging

a powerful tool in the implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data standards (<https://ardc.edu.au/resource/fair-data/>). The area of 3D imaging is an indispensable part of the future of Australia's biodiversity collections.

Priorities for the digital future of Australia's 3D biodiversity objects

Despite the potential for 3D biodiversity data to revolutionise the use of Australia's biodiversity collections, their uptake and use is currently patchy and far below their potential impact. We believe that there are several key obstacles to mobilising and achieving their promise of equitable, future-proof access, which are related to issues of *storage and curation capacity*, *internal support*, as well as a highly fragmented *policy* and *access* landscape, as detailed below.

Nationally based, centrally supported digital storage infrastructure

Virtual 3D digitisation requires vastly larger storage capacity than conventional digitisation (such as photography), ranging from under 100 Mb (simple surface scans) to 50 Gb (Synchrotron or microCT scans). This has created issues with storage since the advent of 3D imaging in the sector nearly two decades ago. Some institutions are able to store digital images on local hard drives; however, most collections lack infrastructure and/or staffing to house them, leaving the external users who acquired them to make decisions regarding storage (and often pay for storage out of research funds). The result is that digital scans are often 'lost' because they cannot be centrally managed, seriously undermining the goals of FAIR digitisation principles.

As it stands, petabytes of data, worth millions of (often taxpayer-funded) dollars, are already scattered across local university servers, individual-owned hard drives, and various storage servers (e.g., Dropbox). Many researchers resort to deposition of 3D files outside the country and beyond Australian jurisdiction because of the better-developed systems there, most commonly on the Duke-University (US) - based MorphoSource platform. Given that the acquisition cost and re-use value of these images far outweighs their storage cost, a unified, well-resourced storage solution is therefore arguably the most urgent issue in this area, together with the processing of the existing tremendous backlog of images.

We also expect the existence of such a local solution under Australian ownership to be a strong motivational influence on institutions and data creators to generate and appropriately publish these valuable 3D datasets. It will also allow for the development of a culture and policy frameworks where deposition of datasets is a requirement, rather than optional. A very successful

example is Genbank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>), a repository for DNA data which has allowed the genetics field to move to mandatory open-access publication of genetics research.

Equitably distributed data and metadata curation capacity

Australia also lacks interfaces in which 3D data can be curated and presented in a way that balances accessibility of the data with oversight by collections. As with storage, many institutions have their own local data management systems with diverse capacity of interacting with specimen records. In addition, the relatively new arrival of this issue means that 3D image curation systems can be severely under-resourced if they even exist. This challenge already exists with the large amount of unrecorded, untraceable data generated by external users. Equitable access of institutions to curation systems that allow them to keep a record of virtual specimens and their uses is therefore a priority with similar urgency to the rapidly increasing amount of 3D data.

Support for well-developed frontline data management

Although not new, 3D imaging still represents a frontier technology for biodiversity collections. Collections staff often lack the tools, resources or policies to appropriately track, store and maintain these data. This is not just the fault of individual institutions, as off-the-shelf solutions to these problems are rarely available. For example, the Content Management Systems (CMS) and Digital Asset Managers (DAMS), which many institutions have invested years of work into, do not directly support 3D data.

This lack represents a rare opportunity in collections-derived data to intervene at a critical, early stage of their development where many issues remain comparatively manageable. However, without collective advocacy and urgency for optimized solutions, 'ground-level' staff within individual institutions are currently left to reinvent the wheel in isolation. Developing solutions with inadequate support and resources could result in short-sighted solutions that will at the very least risk legacy issues and double handling for decades to come. In a worst-case scenario, continued inaction and prolonged use of interim solutions could result in data loss on a monumental scale.

It is also critical that advocacy comes from the right places, as action cannot be left to generators of 3D images. 3D data management must be championed by decision makers and those responsible for running CMS', DAMS', Digital Preservation systems and data image standards.

We therefore recommend that a national level approach to the institutional management of 3D biodiversity data should be considered. 3D data management solutions often encounter national scale issues, such as the challenge of maintaining data sovereignty while ensuring that research data is appropriately FAIR. When developing 3D data management resources, lessons learned from existing national collections resources and driving bodies such as the Council of Heads of Australian Faunal Collections, CSIRO, Atlas of Living Australia, Faunal Collections Informatics Group, and the ARC Centre of Excellence for Australian Biodiversity and Heritage, will be invaluable. Further, 3D data could represent an opportunistic testing ground for future nationally standardized models of specimen data lifecycles online. A collections-centric '3D imaging working group' comprised of decision makers and the people responsible for running CMS', DAMS', Digital Preservation and globally recognised data standards etc., discussing common data management deficits and policy gaps and working to develop national guidelines and directions to inform the development of resources would be a valuable first step.

A national Copyright and IP policy framework

Digitisation of 3D specimens in Australia currently occurs in a governance vacuum, with no guidance on the copyright and intellectual property (IP) implications in 3D acquisition. The context of a collection makes a crucial difference to policies of specimen acquisition, management, and distribution; for example, most museum collections are under state control and thus dependent on local policy (as well as often having independent in-house policies). Others are not sufficiently staffed to determine their policies in the first place and resort to ad-hoc decision making.

The copyright of 3D images derived from biodiversity collections in Australia remains untested in the courts. It might not be achievable to arrive at a nationally unified 3D data policy, but a clear and user-friendly set of resources (such as the fact sheets provided by the Australian Copyright Council - <https://www.copyright.org.au/search?page=1&imprint=info>) or guidelines and clear expectations (for example in terms of FAIR data standard implementation) would provide an ideal framework for the more practical challenges of storage and curation detailed above. This would allow Australian institutions to emulate the very successful digital data policies adopted in US institutions like the American Museum of Natural History or the Smithsonian Institution.

Structures to help prioritise and provide equitable access

Acquisition costs are a major driver of inequity in the access and use of 3D data. For example, the common use of competitive funding in image acquisition incentivises the "monopolisation" of

scans in research and even commercial contexts, particularly in the absence of assertive policies on 3D image publications (see above). An important way forward is therefore the development of strategic and equitable access to 3D acquisition.

A crucial step towards equitable access to 3D access will be building strong partnerships and governance between existing digitisation organisations (e.g. National Imaging Facility, Bioplatforms Australia) and the collections sector. Our committee provides a model for how such partnerships can be developed and expanded. Such a collaboration has the potential to develop a national governance framework to identify and prioritise national collections for digitisation, which our committee has been working on. This would allow prioritisation to digitise objects or specimens that would give value around the areas of food security, biodiversity conservation, invasive species, mineral exploration, agriculture and medicine discoveries. A partnership body like this would also allow the distribution of imaging services based on national need, not individual funding. An excellent existing example is the merit-based application process at The Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation (ANSTO).